

A FIXED POINT THEOREM FOR GENERALIZED WEAK $(\psi - \varphi)$ CONTRACTION IN S -METRIC SPACE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we will show existence and uniqueness of the fixed point for generalized weak $(\psi - \varphi)$ contraction in S -metric space. In addition, we support our result by an example.

INTRODUCTION

Fixed point theory is the branch of Mathematics which developed in 19th century. Fixed point is that point of a self map which remains invariant under the given self map. Banach [2] was the first, who developed a contraction principle to evaluate the fixed point in 1922. Later, the researchers tried to weaken or strong the Banach contraction principle to obtain the new contraction. In 1997, Alber and Gurre [1] generalized the Banach contraction principle by introducing one distance altering function in Hilbert Spaces. In 2001, Rhoades [4] has shown that result of Alber and Gurre is also valid in complete metric space. In 2008, Dutta and Choudhury [3] generalized the result of Rhoades by introducing two distance altering function in complete metric space.

In 2014, by taking three altering distance functions, Shukla and Singh [6] generalized the result of Dutta and Choudhury [3] for complete metric space as follows:

Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and T be a self mapping on X satisfying the following:

$$\psi(d(Tx, Ty)) \leq \psi(d(x, y)) - \varphi(d(x, y)) - \varphi'(d(Tx, x)),$$

where $\psi, \varphi, \varphi' : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ are all continuous and non-decreasing functions with

$$\varphi'(t) = \varphi(t) = 0 = \psi(t) \text{ if and only if } t = 0.$$

Then T has a unique fixed point.

Definition 1.1. [5] Let X be a non-empty set and $S: X \times X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function satisfying the following:

$$SM (1) S(x, y, z) = 0 \text{ if and only if } x = y = z ;$$

$$SM (2) S(x, y, z) \leq S(x, x, t) + S(y, y, t) + S(z, z, t); \text{ for all } x, y, z, t \in X.$$

Then the function S is called S -metric and space (X, S) is called S -metric space.

Lemma 1.2. If (X, S) is called S -metric space, then $S(x, x, y) = S(y, y, x)$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Lemma 1.3. If (X, S) is called S -metric space and $x_n \rightarrow x$ and $y_n \rightarrow y$ in X as $n \rightarrow \infty$ then $S(x_n, x_n, y_n) \rightarrow S(x, x, y)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where $\{x_n\}$ and $\{y_n\}$ are sequences in X .

1. Main Result

Theorem 2.1. Let (X, S) be a complete S -metric space and T be a self mapping on X satisfying the inequality

$$\psi(S(Tx, Tx, Ty)) \leq \psi(S(x, x, y)) - \varphi(S(x, x, y)) - \varphi'(S(Tx, Tx, x)), \tag{2.1}$$

where $\psi, \varphi, \varphi' : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ are all continuous and non-decreasing functions with

$$\varphi'(t) = \varphi(t) = 0 = \psi(t) \text{ if and only if } t = 0.$$

Then T has a unique fixed point.

Proof: For any x_0 that is an element of X , consider an iterative sequence $\{x_n\}$, where $x_n = Tx_{n-1}$ and $Tx_0 = x_1$, where n is any positive integer.

Putting $x = x_{n-1}$ and $y = x_n$ in (2.1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(S(x_n, x_n, x_{n+1})) &\leq \psi(S(x_{n-1}, x_{n-1}, x_n)) - \varphi(S(x_{n-1}, x_{n-1}, x_n)) \\ &\quad - \varphi'(S(x_n, x_n, x_{n-1})), \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

which implies that

$$\psi(S(x_n, x_n, x_{n+1})) < \psi(S(x_{n-1}, x_{n-1}, x_n)),$$

$$S(x_n, x_n, x_{n+1}) < S(x_{n-1}, x_{n-1}, x_n) \text{ (By using monotonic property of } \psi \text{ function).}$$

which implies that, $S(x_n, x_n, x_{n+1})$ is a monotonically decreasing sequence.

It follows that sequence $\{S(x_n, x_n, x_{n+1})\}$ is monotonically decreasing and is bounded below by '0'. So, the sequence $\{S(x_n, x_n, x_{n+1})\}$ converges to some $r \geq 0$, that is,

$$\{S(x_n, x_n, x_{n+1})\} \rightarrow r \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Making $n \rightarrow \infty$ in equation (2.2), we get

$$\psi(r) \leq \psi(r) - \varphi(r) - \varphi'(r),$$

a contradiction unless $r = 0$, as ψ is non-decreasing function.

Hence

$$S(x_n, x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{2.3}$$

Next, we will show that $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. So, let us suppose, if possible, that $\{x_n\}$ is not a Cauchy sequence. Then there exist $\epsilon > 0$ for which we can find two subsequences $\{x_{m(k)}\}$ and $\{x_{n(k)}\}$ of $\{x_n\}$ with $n(k) > m(k) > k$, such that

$$S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}) \geq \epsilon. \tag{2.4}$$

Further for $m(k)$ we can choose $n(k)$ in such a way that it is the smallest integer with $n(k) > m(k)$ and satisfying (2.4).

Then

$$S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}) < \epsilon. \tag{2.5}$$

Now, using (2.4), Lemma 1.2 and SM (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &\leq S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}) = S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}), \\ &\leq 2S(x_{n(k)}, x_{n(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}) + S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}), \\ &\quad = 2S(x_{n(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}) + S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}), \\ &\leq 2S(x_{n(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}) + \epsilon \text{ (by using 2.5)} \end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

Now, taking $k \rightarrow \infty$ and using (2.3) in (2.6), we get

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}) = \epsilon. \tag{2.7}$$

Again, with the help of Lemma 1.2 and SM (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}) &\leq 2S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)-1}) \\ &\quad + S(x_{n(k)}, x_{n(k)}, x_{m(k)-1}), \\ &\leq 2S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)-1}) \\ &\quad + 2S(x_{n(k)}, x_{n(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}) \\ &\quad + S(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1}). \end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

Once again, by same process, we get

$$\begin{aligned} S(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1}) &\leq 2S(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)}) + S(x_{n(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1}, x_{m(k)}), \\ &= 2S(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)}) \\ &\quad + S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}). \end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

Letting $k \rightarrow \infty$ and using (2.3), (2.7) in (2.8) and (2.9), we get

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} S(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1}) = \epsilon. \tag{2.10}$$

Putting $x = x_{m(k)-1}, y = x_{n(k)-1}$ and using (2.4) in the equation (2.1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\epsilon) &\leq \psi(S(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)})) \\ &\leq \psi(S(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1})) - \varphi(S(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1})) \\ &\quad - \varphi'(S(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)-1})), \end{aligned}$$

Taking $k \rightarrow \infty$ and using (2.7) and (2.10), we get

$$\psi(\epsilon) \leq \psi(\epsilon) - \varphi(\epsilon) - \varphi'(\epsilon),$$

which implies that $\epsilon = 0$ (as ψ is monotonic non decreasing function).

a contradiction.

So, $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

Now as (X, S) is a complete S-metric space so $\{x_n\}$ is a convergent sequence in X . Let $\{x_n\}$ converges to z .

Now, putting $x = x_{n-1}$ and $y = z$ in (2.1), we get

$$\psi(S(x_n, x_n, Tz)) \leq \psi(S(x_{n-1}, x_{n-1}, z)) - \varphi(S(x_{n-1}, x_{n-1}, z)) - \varphi'(S(x_n, x_n, x_{n-1}))$$

Taking $k \rightarrow \infty$ and by property of ψ function in the above inequality, we get $Tz = z$.

Uniqueness: If possible, let us suppose that z_1 and z_2 are two distinct fixed points of T .

Putting $x = z_1$ and $y = z_2$ in (2.1), we get

$$\psi(S(Tz_1, Tz_1, Tz_2)) \leq \psi(S(z_1, z_1, z_2)) - \varphi(S(z_1, z_1, z_2)) - \varphi'(S(z_1, z_1, z_2)),$$

implies that

$$\psi(S(z_1, z_1, z_2)) < \psi(S(z_1, z_1, z_2)).$$

This holds only when $S(z_1, z_1, z_2) = 0$.

This implies that

$$z_1 = z_2.$$

This proves the uniqueness of the fixed point.

Example 2.2. Let $X = [0,1]$ and define $S: X^3 \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ as follows:

$$S(x, y, z) = |x - z| + |y - z|.$$

One can check that (X, S) is a complete S-metric space.

Define, $\psi(t) = 4t, \varphi(t) = t = \varphi'(t)$ and $T(x) = \frac{x}{50}$.

Now, evaluate both sides of equation of (2.1),

L.H.S.

$$4 \left\{ \left| \frac{x}{50} - \frac{y}{50} \right| + \left| \frac{x}{50} - \frac{y}{50} \right| \right\} = \frac{4}{25} |x - y|. \quad (2.11)$$

R.H.S.

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(S(x, x, y)) - \varphi(S(x, x, y)) - \varphi'(S(Tx, Tx, x)) &= 8|x - y| - 2|x - y| - 2 \left| \frac{x}{50} - y \right| \\ &= 6|x - y| - 2 \left| \frac{x}{50} - y \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

By comparing equations (2.11) and (2.12) one can easily check that (2.1) holds.

So, by theorem 2.1, T has a unique fixed point.

It can be seen easily that '0' is the unique fixed point of T .

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